

POSITIVE EDUCATION INTERVENTION PROGRAMME OUTCOME ON THE ACADEMIC RESILIENCE OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

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Abstract

One thing inevitable about life is adversities. Difficult situations can be encountered by anyone at anytime and anyplace. One cannot control what can happen but one can definitely learn to respond to situations. How one deals with challenges in life or adversities contributes to a large extent to that person's well-being. The ability required by a person to recover from adversities is resilience. Academic resilience is defined as the ability to effectively deal with setback, stress or pressure in the academic setting. This paper aims to ascertain the outcome of positive education intervention programme on the Academic Resilience of the pre-service teachers. The positive education intervention programme of 30 hours was developed for this purpose. The participants included in the study were 46 and 48 pre-service teachers in the control and experimental group respectively. The findings of the study indicate pre-service teachers from the experimental group have scored higher on Academic Resilience as compared to the pre-service teachers from the control group after controlling the effect of their pre-test scores.

Introduction:

One thing inevitable about life is adversities. Difficult situations can be encountered by anyone at anytime and anyplace. One cannot control what can happen but one can definitely learn to respond to situations. How one deals with challenges in life or adversities contributes to a large extent to that person's well-being. The ability required by a person to recover from adversities is

resilience. Resilience is 'an ability to recover from or adjust easily to misfortune or change' (Merriam-webster.com, 2015)¹. When we see resilience through the perspective of positive psychology it is not only to bounce back from obstacles but to bounce forward.

Identifying characteristics that enable academic achievement and that distinguish individuals who are successful from those who are not, setting intellectual capacity aside, remains a worthy pursuit for educational research and practice. One such characteristic is resilience. Resilience is commonly considered a desirable quality, a core strength to positively influence one's performance, academic achievement, well-being and health (Bartley, et. Al, 2010. Martin & Marsh, 2009)^{2,3} Present research on well-being suggest that students can develop their resilience skills by developing their positive cognitive, affective and behavioral orientations to academic life. Academic resilience is a contributor for improved academic achievement. ⁴ Gonzalez and Padilla (as cited in Waxman, Gray, & Padron, 2003) found that students' sense of belonging to school was a predictor of academic resilience.⁵

Academic resilience is defined as the ability to effectively deal with setback, stress or pressure in the academic Setting.⁶

Resilience shows a positive correlation with psychological well-being (Picardi et al., 2012; Sagone & De Caroli, 2013)⁷. Resilience is also found to be a positive and significant predictor for psychological well-being and this relationship is mediated by optimism. Greater resilience also proves to have greater perception of well-being even at retirement (Nalin, C. P. & Franca. L, 2015).⁸

Institution that demonstrates an ongoing commitment to fostering resilience will end up further facilitating the success of *all* of its students, not just those from marginalized and disadvantaged backgrounds(Morales, E. 2014)⁹. Thus it is valuable goal to foster resilience in students.

Rationale of the Study

Educational institutions are significant agency of formal education, children spend a vast amount of time at this place. During their time at school/ college, they face different situations. Some are good, some are difficult. These adversities can be in terms of poor academic performance, negative teacher feedback, poor peer relations, bullying, meeting project deadlines, managing multiple academic tasks at hand, etc. Such situations can be debilitating to the students. However some academically resilient students respond proactively to such situations and move on

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but some get trapped in the downward spiral of negativity and underperformance. Such students are said to be low on academic resilience. Thus resilience becomes an important quality to be developed in students.

Teachers are role model to these young students. Through direct and indirect ways they contribute in capacity building of their students. Values are something that students can catch from teachers rather than being taught by their teachers. Thus it is a valuable goal to develop capacities of future teachers with skills of resilience.

Review of Related Literature

Gafoor and Kottalil (2015)¹⁰ studied factors influencing academic resilience. 126 protective factors were identified, listed in 19 categories belonging to four areas from where the child draws the strength to fight adversities viz., self, family, school and community. Mallick and Kaur (2016)¹¹ investigated academic resilience among senior secondary school students: influence of learning environment. Study revealed that boys possessed more scores in academic resilience as compared with girls. Urban students possessed high level of academic resilience. Girl students have high level of learning environment as compared with boys. Locality-wise urban students scored significantly high in learning environment as compared with rural students. Significant positive relation was found between learning environment and academic resilience of senior secondary students. Mehar and Madnawat (2018)¹² conducted a comparative study of academic resilience and optimism among students of educated and uneducated parents. The results revealed that there is a significant difference between academic resilience and optimism among students of educated and uneducated parents. Martin & Marsh (2003)¹³ conducted a study to explore academic resilience and the four C's: Confidence, control, composure and commitment. The study demonstrated that academic resilience comprises self-belief (confidence), a sense of control, low anxiety (composure), and persistence (commitment) as measured through administration of the SMS (that measures each of these four dimensions) to 400 Australian high school students. Leon & Trinidad (2012)¹⁴ explored gender and family related factors as predictors of academic motivation and academic resilience among Latino students. Regression analyses were computed and results revealed that perceived academic support from mothers was a significant predictor of academic motivation. In addition, the regression analyses also revealed that perceived academic support from fathers significantly predicted both academic motivation and academic resilience.

Statement of the Problem

Positive education intervention programme outcome on Academic Resilience of the pre-service teachers.

Operational Definition of the Terms

Positive Education: Positive education is defined as enabling the learner to acquire knowledge and skills to develop their well-being.

Academic Resilience: Academic resilience is defined as ability manifested by an individual in two aspects: self- efficacy and Social support and social competence.

- Self- efficacy is the ability to do something or think in a certain way, confidence in academic qualities, disposition to expect positive outcomes and belief in one's ability to influence outcomes in life.
- Social support and social competence consist of care, support and encouragement received from family, friends, teachers and other members of the institution. It is the ability of the person to get along well with others and function constructively in groups.

Aim of the Study

To ascertain the effect of positive education programme on Academic Resilience of pre-service teachers.

Objectives of the Study

1. To compare the pre-test scores on Academic Resilience of the experimental and control group.
2. To compare the post-test scores on Academic Resilience of the experimental and control group after partialling out the effect of pre-test scores.

Null Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test scores on Academic Resilience of the experimental and control group.
2. There is no significant difference in the post-test scores on Academic Resilience of the experimental and control group after partialling out the effect of pre-test scores.

Methodology of the Present Study

In the present research, quasi experimental design of the pre-test post-test, non-equivalent groups type is used. It can be described as follows:

The pre-test-post-test non-equivalent groups design

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$O_1 \times O_2$

$O_3 \times O_4$

Where,

O_1 and O_3 = Pre-test Scores

O_2 and O_4 = Post- test Scores

X : Experimental Group

C : Control Group.

Sample of the Study

In the present study, the sample has been selected consisting of one intact class each of S. Y. B. Ed. students from two different colleges of education situated in the Greater Mumbai. The study adopted a two-stage sampling technique. At the first stage, colleges were selected using simple random sampling technique (lottery method). At the second stage, students were selected from these two colleges using cluster sampling technique. The experimental comprised of 48 student-teachers and the control group consisted of 46 student- teachers.

Tool of the Study

In the present study following tools were used by the researcher to collect the data:
Academic Resilience Scale (D'souza and Pandya, 2017).

Intervention Programme: The positive education intervention programme was conducted in the experimental group. The positive education intervention programme comprised of five modules, namely, resilience, positive emotions, positive relationships, character strengths and meaning in life. The duration of the programme was of 30 hours. Each module of the programme was divided into sessions. Every session was further divided into some activities.

Techniques of Data Analysis: The present research used statistical techniques of t-test, ANCOVA and Wolf's formula.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test scores on Academic Resilience of the experimental and control group.

This hypothesis was tested with the objective of comparing the initial status of the experimental and control group on Academic Resilience. The technique used for testing this null hypothesis is the t- test.

The following table shows the relevant statistics of the pre- test scores of Academic Resilience of the participants of the experimental and control group.

Table 1: Pre- test scores of ARS of EG and CG

Group	N	Mean	t	P	L. o. s
EG	48	133.50	2.76	0.007	NS
CG	46	124.61			

The preceding table shows that the t- ratio for ARS is 2.67 with P= 0.007. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is a significant difference between the EG and CG on pre- test of ARS at 0.01 level of significance. The mean ARS of EG is higher than the mean ARS of CG. Thus it can be stated that the pre- test ARS of EG is significantly greater than the pre- test ARS of CG.

2. There is no significant difference in the post-test scores on Academic Resilience of the experimental and control group after partialling out the effect of pre-test scores.

This hypothesis was tested using ANCOVA. The mean ARS scores of the EG and the CG differ significantly so the technique of ANCOVA was applied to partial out the effect of pre- test scores from the post- test scores of ARS.

The following table shows the relevant statistics of the post- test scores of Academic Resilience of the participants of the experimental and control group after partialling out the effect of pre- test ARS.

Table 2: Post- test scores of ARS of EG and CG

Groups	Experimental	Control
Observed Mean	144.44	123.35
Adjusted Mean	142.14	125.74

ANCOVA determines whether the adjusted post- test means of the two groups differ significantly from each other.

Table 3 shows the relevant statistics of ANCOVA for post- test mean ARS of EG and CG

Table 3: ANCOVA for post- test mean of ARS of EG AND CG

Sources of variation	SS	df	MS	F- ratio	P
Adjusted Means (A)	5831.12	1	5831.12	31.77	<0.001
Adjusted error (B)	16702.37	91	183.54		
Adjusted total (A + B)	22533.49	92			

It can be stated that there is a significant difference in the post test scores of pre- service teachers' Academic Resilience from experimental and control group. The mean ARS score of pre-service teachers from EG is significantly greater than that of CG.

DISCUSSION: The findings reveal that the pre-service teachers from the experimental group have scored higher on Academic Resilience as compared to the pre-service teachers from the control group after controlling the effect of their pre- test scores. This favourable effect can be attributed to the positive education programme which led to the development of academic resilience scores in the pre-service teachers of the experimental group. The positive education programme oriented the participants to various skills that help develop academic resilience. The pre-service teachers from the experimental group also participated in the activities that provided them a first-hand experience of applying resilience skills in life. This led to the development of Academic resilience in the pre-service teachers in the experimental group.

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